

AWARENESS OF CYBER-CRIME AMONG THE B.ED. STUDENTS IN WEST BENGAL

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ABSTRACT

India's rapid technological advancement and the widespread adoption of digital technologies have made the country increasingly vulnerable to various forms of cybercrime. The rise in online transactions, social media usage and internet-enabled devices has created space for cybercriminals to exploit. Therefore, we must remain vigilant against digital frauds that occur over the internet. Teachers are the center of the teaching-learning process. Many students fall victim to cybercrime attacks. Therefore, educating our teachers about these digital crimes is crucial to fostering a digitally healthy world. This article aimed to assess the awareness of B.Ed. students in West Bengal. A standardized Cyber-crime Awareness Scale was used, developed by Rajasekar (2011), to collect the relevant data from 171 B.Ed. Students from Six NCTE recognized institutions in the state. The study found slight differences in awareness levels, with female students and students with a science background showing higher awareness than their counterparts. Moreover, students from urban and semi-urban areas showed higher awareness than those from rural areas. However, this study highlights the necessity of integrating cybercrime education into teacher training programs. Hence, the future researchers can explore the pros and cons of digital security and can help to build a more cyber resilient generation.

Keywords: Cyber-Crime, Awareness, B.Ed. Students, Attitude.

INTRODUCTION

In the digital age, the rise of cybercrime has become a growing concern worldwide, and India is no exception to it. The rapid expansion of the internet and advancements in Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) has transformed the way we live, work, and interact. However, this digital transformation has also led to a significant increase in criminal activities, commonly known as cybercrime (Halder & Jaishankar, 2010).

Cybercrime takes many forms, including hacking, child pornography, cyber stalking, malware, phishing, ransomware, cyberbullying, online scams, and more (Jain & Srivastava,

2014). With its large and rapidly expanding population of internet users, India has become a prime target for cybercriminals, particularly in rural areas where people may have less awareness of digital security (Kumar, 2016). The country has seen a surge in various types of cyber-attacks, such as financial fraud, identity theft, online harassment, and data breaches.

This trend is largely attributed to the widespread use of smartphones, e-commerce platforms, and digital payment systems, which provide cybercriminals with opportunities to exploit vulnerabilities in these technologies. A summary of reported cybercrime cases in 2022, as documented by the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), highlights the extent of these crimes across Indian states and the districts of West Bengal.

Fig. 1: No. of Cases Registered (Cyber Crime) across the States

Source: Cyber Crime, NCRB (2022)

In 2022, there was a notable increase in reported cybercrimes in India compared to the previous year. According to the latest NCRB report (2022), Telangana recorded the highest number of cybercrime cases with 15,297 incidents, followed by Karnataka with 12,556 cases and Uttar Pradesh with 10,117 cases. Therefore, it is recommended that these states prioritize strengthening cyber security measures and enhancing public awareness about cybercrimes.

On the other hand, Mizoram, Nagaland, and Daman & Diu reported the fewest cases, each with fewer than 10 incidents, it is advisable for these states to take proactive measures to prevent potential digital threats.

Although West Bengal’s cybercrime rate is not as high as that of some other states, there is a strong possibility that the number of cases may rise if appropriate steps are not taken promptly. The Figure 2 demonstrates the district-wise distribution of registered cases in West Bengal.

Fig. 2: District-wise No. of Cases registered for Cyber Crimes in WB

Source : Cyber Crime, NCRB (2022)

The above statistics show that Kolkata, Purba Medinipur and Barrackpur PC reported the highest number of cases, with 75, 34, and 27 cases, respectively. On the other hand, a few districts, such as Darjeeling, Purulia, and Krishnagar, have reported no cases.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Awareness of cybercrime plays a significant role in mitigating digital fraud, which predominantly occurs over the internet. The incidence of such crimes has gradually increased, particularly since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, during which cybercriminals gained partial access to users’ personal information due to expanded online activity and digital vulnerability. In response, several studies have been investigated to understand cybercrime awareness across different regions and demographic groups.

Goel (2014) studied among B.Ed. students in the Sonitpur district and found that cybercrime awareness was significantly influenced by location and academic stream but not by gender. Similar findings were reported by Suvera and Tailor (2020), Velmurugan and Ramachandran

(2022), and Chaudhuri (2022), who all observed significant variations in awareness based on academic stream, gender and locality.

Gender has emerged as a particularly complex and contested variable in this context. While studies by Muthulakshmi and Kumar (2017), Vinnarasi and Rajkumar (2021), Maurya and Suryavanshi (2023), and Bala (2022) revealed significant gender-based differences in cybercrime awareness, other researchers, including Goel (2014), Choudhary (2020), and Sahu and Shukla (2024), reported no such variation. These divergent findings highlight the nuanced and context-specific influence of gender on cybercrime awareness.

Academic stream has also been identified as an important determinant. Goel (2014) and Choudhary (2020) observed that students enrolled in professional courses tended to demonstrate higher levels of awareness. This trend was further supported by the findings of Vinnarasi and Rajkumar (2021), Chaudhuri (2022), and Velmurugan and Ramachandran (2022).

Locality remains another key factor influencing cybercrime awareness. Goel (2014) and Bhutia and Passah (2019) reported lower awareness among rural B.Ed. trainees, which was attributed to limited access to digital resources and exposure. Consistent with this, Kumar et al. (2021), Bera and Chel (2020), Bala (2022), and Sahu and Shukla (2024) found higher levels of awareness among urban students, particularly urban females. However, this trend was contested by Vinnarasi and Rajkumar (2021), who reported no significant difference based on locality.

In conclusion, the literature suggests that cybercrime awareness among B.Ed. trainees is shaped by a complex interplay of demographic and academic variables, most notably gender, academic stream and locality. These findings highlight the need for context-sensitive interventions to enhance digital literacy and cyber security awareness in teacher education programs.

NEED OF THE STUDY

The need for this study on cybercrime awareness stems from the growing threat the cybercrime poses to society, particularly to individuals who may lack adequate knowledge of digital safety. Cybercrime awareness involves educating individuals and organizations about various cyber threats, vulnerabilities, and risks in the digital landscape, equipping them with essential knowledge to protect themselves against potential harm (Jain & Srivastava, 2014; Kumar et al., 2021; Suvera & Tailor, 2020).

In an increasingly interconnected society where technology is embedded into daily life, cyber threats are rapidly evolving, making detection challenging and leaving many individuals exposed to risk. The lack of education and awareness is a critical factor that exacerbates the spread of cybercrime. As such, efforts are being made by governments to proactively counter cyber threats, underscoring the importance of educating all citizens, particularly those involved in the education sector, about cyber safety.

Teacher trainees in Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) programs are positioned as future educators for the next generation, making it essential for them to cultivate awareness and understanding of cyber threats and digital safety. Their familiarity with cybercrime prevention

is crucial as they prepare to guide future students in safe digital practices. To address this need, integrating cybercrime awareness into B.Ed. curricula, along with organizing workshops and seminars, can significantly enhance teacher trainees' preparedness and confidence in digital spaces. This study, therefore, seeks to explore the importance of cybercrime awareness among B.Ed. trainees, aiming to promote a proactive, informed attitude towards technology and online security.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

This paper aims to assess the level of cyber-crime awareness among B.Ed. students in West Bengal, considering factors such as gender, location, and academic streams.

HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses have been framed for this study:

- **H_{o1}** : There would be no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. students in their level of awareness towards cybercrime.
- **H_{o2}** : There would be no significant difference between arts and science stream B.Ed. students in their level of awareness towards cyber-crime.
- **H_{o3}** : There would be no significant difference between rural and urban B.Ed. students in their level of awareness towards cybercrime.
- **H_{o4}** : There would be no significant difference between urban and semi-urban B.Ed. students in their level of awareness towards cybercrime.
- **H_{o5}** : There would be no significant difference between rural and semi-urban B.Ed. students in their level of awareness towards cybercrime.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive research approach. The population comprises of all the B.Ed. students studied in the NCTE recognised Teacher Education Institutions in West Bengal. For this study, the investigators have collected the data from 171 B.Ed. students studied in different TEIs at Cooch Behar district by using simple random technique. The demographic details of the respondents based on gender (male and female), location (Rural, Urban and Semi-Urban) and stream (arts and science) is given in Table 1.

Table 1 : Demographic Details of the Respondents

Main Variable	Categorical Variable	No. of Respondents	% of response	Total
Gender	Male	69	40	171
	Female	102	60	
Location	Rural	113	66	171
	Urban	38	22	
	Semi-Urban	20	12	
Stream	Arts	130	76	171
	Science	41	24	

After collection of relevant data, the researchers have used descriptive as well as inferential statistics like Mean, Standard Deviation and t-Test to assess the hypotheses.

Tool used for the study

The Cyber-Crime Awareness Scale (CCAS), developed by Rajasekar (2011), have been used in order to measure the cyber-crime awareness level among the B.Ed. students in West Bengal. This scale consists of 36 statements, including positive and negative statements. The details of positive and negative statements are as follows.

Statement Type	Item No.	Total
Positive Statements	1, 2, 4, 6, 7, 9, 11, 12, 14, 17, 18, 20, 21, 23, 24, 26, 27, 29, 30, 34, 36	21
Negative Statements	3, 5, 8, 10, 13, 15, 16, 19, 22, 25, 28, 31, 32, 33, 35	15

Each statement has five (5) alternative responses, namely “Strongly Agree”, “Agree”, “Undecided”, “Disagree”, and “Strongly Disagree”. For the positive statements, the scoring is done as 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 and for the negative statements it scored as 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5, respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data has been analysed based on the scores obtained by the respondents. First, the scores were organized according to the level of awareness achieved. Then, each hypothesis was tested to measure the significant differences between the mean scores of the considered variables (gender, location, and streams) using the Student’s t-test. The findings of the study are as follows.

Table 2: Awareness Level achieved by the Respondents

Score Range	No. of Respondents	%	Awareness Level
36 to 98	1	0.58	Low Level
99 to 107	2	1.16	Below average Level
108 to 122	27	15.78	Average Level
123 to 132	46	26.90	High Level
143 to 180	95	55.55	Excellent Level

Regarding the level of cyber-crime awareness, it was observed that a significant percentage of respondents, 55%, achieved an ‘Excellent Level,’ while only 0.58% and 1.16% were found to have ‘Low Level’ and ‘Below Average Level’ awareness, respectively (see Table 2).

Testing of Hypotheses

Ho1: There would be no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. students in their level of awareness towards cybercrime.

Table 3: Difference between the Awareness of B.Ed. students towards Cyber-crime based on gender (Male and Female)

Sl. No.	Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	SEM	df	t-value	Remark
1.	Male	69	134.09	13.118	1.579	169	0.704	Not Significant*
2.	Female	102	135.55	13.449	1.332			

*at 0.05 level of significance

Table 3 reveals that the mean value of male students is found to be 134.09 and 135.55 for female students. It indicates that the mean score of the female students has found slight higher than the male students. The obtained value of t is 0.704 which is much lesser than the critical value of t at 0.05 level of significance (1.98) against 169 degrees of freedom (df).

Thus, it can be concluded that there is found no significant difference between the male and female B.Ed. students towards cybercrime awareness. Hence, the null hypothesis is retained at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho2: There would be no significant difference between arts and science stream B.Ed. students in their level of awareness towards cyber-crime.

Table 4: Difference between the Awareness of B.Ed. students towards Cyber-crime based on Stream (Arts and Science)

Sl. No.	Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	SEM	df	t-value	Remark
1.	Arts	138	134.20	13.098	1.115	169	1.541	Not Significant*
2.	Science	33	138.15	13.850	2.411			

*at 0.05 level of significance

Data in Table 4 reveals that the mean value of arts students is found to be 134.20 and 138.15 for the students belonging to science stream. It is indicated that the mean score of the science stream students has found slight higher than the arts students. The obtained value of t is 1.541 which is much lesser than the critical value of t at 0.05 level of significance (1.98) against 169 degrees of freedom (df).

Thus, it can be concluded that no significant difference is found between the arts and science B.Ed. students towards cybercrime awareness. Hence, again the null hypothesis is retained at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho3: There would be no significant difference between rural and urban B.Ed. students in their level of awareness towards cybercrime.

Table 5: Difference between the Awareness of B.Ed. students towards Cyber-crime based on location (Rural and Urban)

Sl. No.	Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	SEM	df	t-value	Significant at 0.05
1.	Rural	114	132.57	13.017	1.219	169	2.219	Significant
2.	Urban	37	138.08	13.459	2.213			

**at 0.05 level of significance*

Results in Table 5 illustrates that the mean value of rural students is found to be 132.57 and 138.08 for the students belonging to urban areas. Therefore, it is indicated that the mean score of the urban students is much higher than the students belonging to rural areas. The obtained t-value is 2.219 which is much higher than the critical value of t at 0.05 level of significance (1.98) with 169 degrees of freedom (df).

Thus, it can be concluded that there exists a significant difference between the rural and urban B.Ed. students in their awareness towards cybercrime. Consequently, the null hypothesis cannot be retained at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho4: There would be no significant difference between urban and semi-urban B.Ed. students in their level of awareness towards cybercrime.

Table 6: Difference between the Awareness of B.Ed. students towards Cyber-crime based on location (Urban and Semi-urban).

Sl. No.	Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	SEM	df	t-value	Significant at 0.05
1.	Urban	37	138.08	13.459	2.213	169	1.354	Not Significant*
2.	Semi-Urban	20	142.80	10.636	3.378			

**at 0.05 level of significance*

Table 6 shows that the mean value of urban students is found to be 138.08 and 142.80 for semi-urban students. Thus, it is indicated that the mean score of the semi-urban students has found much higher than the students lived in urban areas. The obtained value of 't' is 1.354 which is much lesser than the critical value of t at 0.05 level of significance (1.98) against 169 degrees of freedom (df).

Thus, it can be said that no significant difference exists between urban and semi-urban B.Ed. students in terms of cybercrime awareness; hence, the null hypothesis cannot be retained at the 0.05 level of significance.

Ho5: There would be no significant difference between rural and semi-urban B.Ed. students in their level of awareness towards cybercrime.

Table 7: Difference between the Awareness of B.Ed. students towards Cyber-crime based on location (Rural and Semi-urban)

Sl. No.	Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	SEM	df	t-value	Significant at 0.05
1.	Rural	114	132.57	13.017	1.219	169	3.322	Significant*
2.	Semi-Urban	20	142.80	10.636	2.378			

**at 0.05 level of significance*

The above table (Table 7) indicates that the mean value for semi-urban students (142.80) is significantly higher than that for rural students (132.57). The calculated t-value is 3.322, which exceeds the critical value of t at 0.05 level of significance (1.98) with 169 degrees of freedom (df).

This result indicates a significant difference in cybercrime awareness between rural and semi-urban B.Ed. students. Consequently, the null hypothesis cannot be retained at the 0.05 level of significance. It is also observed that students from rural areas tend to be more susceptible to cybercrime victimization.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The findings of this study explore the levels of cyber-crime awareness among B.Ed. students based on gender, stream and location. Each of these factors reveals distinct trends in students' understanding of cyber-crime, which could inform targeted educational interventions and awareness programs in the B.Ed. curriculum.

The study finds no statistically significant difference in cyber-crime awareness levels between male and female B.Ed. students, corroborating results from earlier studies (Choudhary, 2020; Sahu & Shukla, 2024). These results suggest that both male and female students have similar awareness levels about cyber-crime, indicating a gender-neutral understanding of digital safety and security issues. However, despite the lack of significant difference, the mean awareness score of female students (135.55) was slightly higher than that of male students (134.09). This could point to a subtle difference in engagement or exposure to cyber-crime information among female students. While earlier studies support the lack of significant difference, contrasting findings from studies like Suvera & Tailor (2020), Vinnarasi & Rajkumar (2021), and Velmurugan & Ramachandran (2022) indicate a possible gender difference in cyber-crime awareness.

In terms of academic stream, the results reveal no significant difference in cyber-crime awareness between B.Ed. students from arts and science backgrounds (Velmurugan & Ramachandran, 2022). However, the mean score for science students (138.15) was notably higher than for students in the arts or social sciences (134.20). This pattern suggests that students from scientific disciplines may possess a stronger foundation in or interest towards

technological and cyber-related subjects, likely due to curriculum exposure to topics in computer science or data security. This subtle but consistent trend indicates a potential benefit in incorporating basic cyber-crime awareness into the B.Ed. curriculum across all disciplines to ensure a more balanced understanding among future educators, who may go on to teach in varied fields.

The study also highlights a significant difference in cyber-crime awareness between rural and urban B.Ed. students, aligning with findings from Sahu & Shukla (2024) and Kumar et al. (2021). Urban students showed higher awareness levels, with a mean score of 138.08, compared to rural students, who had a mean score of 132.57. This finding indicates that urban students might have greater exposure to digital technologies, media, and educational resources, which enhances their awareness of cyber-crime threats. In contrast, rural students might have limited access to digital literacy resources, leading to a lower awareness of cyber-crime risks. This significant discrepancy noises for tailored educational programs focused on improving cyber-crime awareness in rural areas to bridge the digital literacy gap and promote equal digital safety understanding across different geographic areas.

CONCLUSION

The present study concludes that cybercrime awareness among trainee teacher in West Bengal is a vital issue, especially given the rapid growth of cyber-related threats globally and within India. With the sample of 171 B.Ed. students, the study assesses awareness levels across gender, location, and academic stream. B.Ed. students generally have similar levels of awareness regarding cybercrime, regardless of their gender, academic background and location. Although slight differences were noted, female students and science background's students had higher awareness than their counterparts. Students of urban and semi-urban area showed higher awareness than those from rural areas. The findings of this study indicate the varying degrees of cyber-crime awareness among different groups, suggesting gaps in knowledge that could make some students more vulnerable to cyber-crimes. Although West Bengal has the lower number of Cybercrime cases than other state, the risk of future escalation remains high without proactive education and awareness. This study highlights the necessity of integrating cyber-crime education into teacher training programs, so future educators can better understand digital security and help to build a more cyber-resilient generation.

REFERENCES

- Bala, R. (2022). A Study of Cyber Crime Awareness among B.Ed. Students. *PARIPEX - Indian Journal of Research*, 11(4), 29-30.
- Bera, S. and Chel, M.M. (2020). A Study on Awareness among Women in Educational Institutions towards Cybercrime. *IISRR international journal of research*, 6(3), 122-129.
- Bhutia, Y. and Passah, E.R. (2019). Cyber Crime Awareness among Student-Teacher of B.Ed. in Relation to Internet Usage. *Learning Community*, 10(1), 17-27.

- Chaudhuri, S. (2022). A Study on Awareness among the B. Ed. College Students Towards Cybercrime. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 27(11), 05-10.
- Choudhary, M. (2020). Cyber crime awareness among higher education students from Haryana with respect to various demographical variables. *Pal Arch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(7), 14454-14461.
- Goel, U. (2014). Awareness among B.Ed Teacher Training towards Cyber-crime – A Study, *Learning Community*, 5(2-3), 107-117.
- Halder, D., & Jaishankar, K. (2010). Cyber Victimization in India: A Baseline Survey Report (2010). *RELX Group (Netherlands)*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1759708>
- Jain, N. & Srivastava, V. (2014). Cyber Crime Changing Everything – An Empirical Study. *International Journal of Computer Application*, 1(4), 76-87.
- Kumar, P N V. (2016). Growing Cyber-crimes in India: A survey. *International Conference on Data Mining and Advanced Computing (SAPIENCE), Ernakulam, India*, 246-251. <https://doi.org/10.1109/sapience.2016.7684146>
- Kumar, S., Grewal, K.K., & Khosla, M. (2021). Cyber Crime Awareness among Teacher Trainees. *International Advanced Research Journal in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 8(6), 471-473.
- Maurya, S., & Suryavanshi, P. (2023). Pilot study: Cyber crime awareness in college-going students in KMCL University. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 11(5), 1798-1809.
- Muthulakshmi, R. and Kumar, T.R. (2017). Awareness of Cyber Crimes Among B.Ed. Students - A Gender Wise Analysis. *Indian Journal of Applied Research*, 7(8), 570-571.
- National Crime Records Bureau. (2022). Home. Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of India. <https://www.ncrb.gov.in/>
- Sahu, M., & Shukla, P. (2024). A Study on Cyber-Crime Awareness among Students in Chhattisgarh. *Journal of Ravishankar University*, 30(1), 54-60.
- Suvera, P., & Tailor, P. R. (2020). Cyber-crime awareness: a comparative study of male and female B.Ed. trainees. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 8(1), 361-365.
- Velmurugan, P., & Ramachandran, R. (2022). A study on Cyber Crime Awareness among B.Ed. Students. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*. 9(11), 1-6.
- Vinnarasi, L., & Nirmal, R.V. (2021). Awareness on Cyber Crime among B.ED. Students. *John Foundation Journal of EduSpark*, 3(4), 36-42.